

Electron charge made from normal electromagnetic flux

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Abstract

We herein consider that the electron is nothing more or extraordinary than a dynamic manifold of normal electromagnetic flux in the vacuum similar to the electromagnetic flux we observe in the field of a magnet or solenoid or the field across the plates of a capacitor. Therefore, our research proposes an answer to the millennium question and unsolved mystery in physics of what the “electron charge” actually is.

1. Introduction

As we have previously described in our model [1] [2] related and experiment [3] [4] publications, the free “electron charge” being at rest and with no translational motion, is a specific Euclidean geometry and finite Cartesian dimensions, coherent dynamic electromagnetic (EM) flux charge formation (i.e. manifold) or else self-sustaining and stable coaxial dipole-vortex distortion inside the quantum vacuum energy field permeating all space-time, see Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Electron Charge as a finite and dynamic physically spinning EM flux manifold in the vacuum [1-4]. See [animation link](#). On the right of the Fig.1 we see the resemblance with the flux in the static field of a magnet or solenoid.

All and each helical line or else described as a closed loop helical fiber, collectively on the finite dimensions horn spheroid manifold shown in **Fig.1** consist the total “charge flux” of an electron at rest and with no translational motion [1] [2]. These helix flux lines shown at a static moment in space-time are not different from the EM flux lines we observe of

the field of a magnet when we sprinkle iron filings over or the field across the plates of capacitor (i.e. electric field flux made visible using semolina seeds).

Our novel theoretical spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ fiber model of the EM charge flux of the electron [1] [2] and also observed or emulated in our experiments [3] [4] and its static snapshot in time imprint, illustrated in **Fig.1**, is dynamic thus a physically revolving and spinning in superposition in a complex rotational motion of the EM charge flux of the intrinsic field of the electron and its confined mass. See [animation link](#) .

2. Electron charge as a manifold of revolving and spinning EM vacuum flux closed – loop fibers

As described before, the intrinsic charge flux manifold of the electron can be analyzed as shown in **Fig.1** physically as being a collection of discrete dynamic complex rotation helical EM flux fiber loops [1] [2].

Nevertheless, our model [1-4] and flux manifold is fundamental and cannot be described effectively by a dimensionless singularity point in space-time as conventionally described usually in the literature. Therefore, our electron model is closer to a finite “string” model with the single “EM flux fiber loop” being the physical irreducible, elementary and fundamental quanta and theoretical cut-off set in our model. Going deeper, our electron model can be emulated by a single such dynamic complex at relativistic speed rotating helical EM flux fiber loop which can also be referred to as a single deformed and “spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ twisted” and physically spinning in 3D space-time photon or soliton [1], **Fig.2**. See [animation link](#).

Fig. 2 The elementary (i.e. fundamental and irreducible) quanta in the charge flux intrinsic spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ fiber model of the electron [1].

Notice most importantly, that this above shown in **Fig.2** normal EM flux in the vacuum helical-twisted single loop also we refer to as “fiber” [1] is fundamental thus irreducible and cannot be further described by the evolution (i.e. motion) of a dimensionless singularity point in our model and theory [1] [2]. The theoretical reason of why we consider this EM flux fiber loop shown in **Fig.2** as being as close as “rigid” and the elementary quanta cut-off limit in our model and theory? Is because we assume as also conventionally stated in the literature that in general EM flux observed in any field is a static coherent stream of so-called off-shell “virtual photons” which however these photons do not resemble normal photons thus do not propagate at the speed of light c in the vacuum or any other speed. In other words virtual photons of the flux in static EM fields are considered as timeless (i.e. static) or effectively as non-local and instantaneous action. Virtual photons in a static E-M field do not propagate along flux lines at the speed of light c [5-8].

Therefore, according to the existing literature, a static “EM flux field line or loop” cannot be described physically and fundamentally by any motion and kinetic energy using a point-quanta because the virtual photons are not translating in space (not propagating) inside and along such a line or loop. Thus, the line or loop in our case is by itself fundamental and **cannot be physically reduced or emulated using a moving (evolving) dimensionless point.**

3. Conclusion

In this brief outline description of our model proposing a physical explanation and description of the intrinsic charge of the electron, we emphasize its nature and resemblance with normal EM flux we observe in static fields and that it is not fundamentally any different or exotic. Also why virtual photons of the EM static flux considered in our theory as being actually physical (i.e. not mathematical artifacts of the theory) and directly unobservable are the reason why a single helical EM flux fiber loop in our finite-dimensions model must be considered as being the fundamental, elementary and irreducible quanta of our novel electron spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ charge flux model [1] [2] that cannot be further described by the evolution of a moving dimensionless point. Essentially, our finite electron model is geometrically and topologically not point-like but rather decrypted by a string (i.e. fiber) fundamental loop of energy.

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